

FEATURES OF THE IMPACT OF HIGHER EDUCATION ON THE ECONOMIC GROWTH OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Dilmurod Khamidullaevich Nabiev

Rector of Karshi State University, Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor;

Akram Odilovich Ochilov

Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor, Academician of Turan Academy of Sciences, Karshi State University;

Muborak Juraevna Raimova

Karshi State University;

Mashkhura Egamberdievna Ostonova

Karshi State University;

Zebo Eshmakhmatovna Normurodova

Karshi State University

Abstract. Along with human resources and capital, lifelong education in general, in particular higher education, can have a significant impact on the economic growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This article examines the problems and achievements of educational and innovation systems, as well as their role in stimulating economic growth in Uzbekistan. The results of the study revealed a relationship between the number of highly qualified personnel with higher education and economic growth in Uzbekistan. An assessment of the regression with GDP growth as a dependent variable and the number of graduates, costs per graduate, and the accumulated average year of study as independent variables revealed a relationship between higher education and economic growth in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, graduates, higher education, economic growth, regression.

Introduction

Analysis of statistical materials (<https://ru.wikipedia.org>, 2020) on the level of world literacy shows that this indicator, in particular, in Norway and Spain is 100%, in Russia 99.7%, in Japan and Switzerland 99, 0%, Singapore 98.1%, Turkey 95.6%, Brazil 92.5%, India 71.2%, Pakistan 57.9%, and Uzbekistan 96.9%. However, the top three in the ranking of countries in the world in terms of the education index is Germany (with an index of 0.943); Norway (with an index of 0.930) and the UK (with an index of 0.928). And the Republic of Uzbekistan occupies 71st place in this rating. This means that Uzbekistan is among the leading countries in terms of literacy. This indicates that school attendance is very high, which is not surprising when you consider that secondary education is compulsory in Uzbekistan and schools are under state control. Speaking about the model of reforming the education system in Uzbekistan and the experience of its implementation, it is important to note that about 35% of the population of Uzbekistan are children under 16 and 60% are young people under 30. In world education, Uzbekistan has a relatively high education index and is proportionally higher than the life expectancy and GDP indices, on average 0.77. This shows the importance of education, especially

higher education, in Uzbekistan. At the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the country has begun to form in Uzbekistan the foundation of a new Renaissance era in Uzbekistan - the Third Renaissance. Mirziyoyev (2020) emphasized about this, "Since ancient times, the issue of upbringing and education has always had an urgent meaning. How do the developed countries of the world achieve high progress and prosperity? Isn't it because of the tremendous focus on science and education? That is why in recent years, in order to comprehensively develop the country, build a new Uzbekistan, radical reforms, as in all other areas, are being carried out in the education system. New horizons in the development of the sphere, undoubtedly, are opened by the recently adopted "Law On Education". Our main goal has been the formation in Uzbekistan of the foundation of a new Renaissance era - the Third Renaissance through large-scale democratic reforms, including in the education system. As history shows, our land, located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, from time immemorial has been one of the centers of high civilization and culture. The rich scientific and cultural heritage of the people, ancient writings, unique architectural monuments, rare manuscripts, and various artifacts testify to the three thousand-year history of our country. It is no accident that I mentioned the words of Aristotle earlier. It is well known with the torch of science, which flashed brightly in Greece in ancient times, was re-lit in Central Asia in the IX-XII centuries. This was the period of the First Renaissance on our land, when a whole galaxy of leading figures of science appeared, whose names and works are still widely known throughout the world today. Muhammad Khorezmi, Ahmad Fergani, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Zamakhshari and dozens of other scientists, with their scientific activities and discoveries of world significance, have made a huge contribution to universal human development. The creation of a great empire by Sahibkiran Amir Temur in the 15th century, which was later ruled by his worthy descendants, was the beginning of the Second Renaissance in our region. She gave the world outstanding scientists - Kazizoda Rumi, Mirzo Ulugbek, Giyosiddin Koshi, Ali Kushchi, great poets Lutfi, Sakkoki, Hafiz Khorezmi, Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Babur and so on. During both Renaissances, our people, thanks to their enormous potential, reached the highest peaks in development, and this gives us a sense of pride. As popular wisdom says, "The river of life does not stand on." Today, relying on the invaluable heritage of our people, we can rightfully say that we have all the opportunities to create the foundation of a new Renaissance in Uzbekistan. It all depends on how wisely we will use this unique potential. Today we have set ourselves a strategic task - to create the foundation of the Third Renaissance, and we regard it as a national idea. The systems of pre-school, school, higher and secondary specialized education, scientific and cultural institutions are four interconnected links of the future Renaissance. We consider kindergarten educators, school teachers, professors and teachers, scientific and creative intelligentsia as four most important pillars in shaping the era of the new Renaissance. I am sure that dear parents will support this initiative and, of course, will become the fifth link, the fifth pillar of the new Renaissance. And this will serve as the most solid foundation for the development of our spiritual and educational life". In this regard, the purpose of the study is to analyze and criterial assessment of the quality training of specialists with higher education in Uzbekistan and to determine the relationship between the number of highly qualified personnel with the indicator of economic growth.

Literature review

It is obvious that, cognitive skills have a substantial effect on economic growth of any

country. Many economists have been interested in learning not only the effect of quantity of education but also the effect of quality of education on economic growth since 1970s. Barro (1999) examined the schooling quality and economic growth while Hanushek and Kimko (2000), Hanushek and Woessmann (2007) had studied the relationship between quality of education and economic growth. Hanushek, Kim and Woessmann have measured the quality of education based on cognitive skills in mathematics and science whereas Barro (1999) uses data on internationally test scores to measure the schooling quality and these researchers have found that, qualitative education has a strong and robust influence on economic growth. In this empirical research, the main issue will be to discuss the direct correlation between quantity of higher education and economic growth in Uzbekistan and to find out whether skilled labor is more important than the quantity of educated workforce in Uzbekistan.

The researchers, Eduardo and Marcio Laurini (2010) from Insper Institute of Education and Research and IbmeC Business School, have presented new evidence on the role of cognitive skills in Economic Development. An article by Dr. Robert B. Kozma, (2008) provides good understanding of knowledge economy and its contribution to economic growth. He refers that, the creation and sharing knowledge feed into the economy to generate knowledge-driven, virtuous cycle sustainable growth, which reflects the knowledge economy that brings a country sustainable growth for their economy. The researcher illustrates the case of Finland as an excellent example. In the early 1990s, Finnish economy faced a significant recession with an average GDP growth rate of -3.68% from 1990 to 1993.

However, Lant Pritchett (1996) does not support the ideas of other researchers who consider the positive relationship of massive education to economic growth. No one denies that there is a partial correlation between enrollment ratios and economic growth. However, Pritchett (1996) advised not to use this partial correlation in assessing the impact of human capital change. He considers that, there must be another interpretation for the partial correlation of enrollment rates and economic growth. Uzbekistan's researchers from Center for Social Research Yakov Asminkin and Olga Nemirovskaya (2007), Tashkent have conducted research on education reforms in Uzbekistan. They provided qualitative analysis of the current situation of national higher education and suggested the ways of deepening the reform.

The results of the study by A. Maddison (1991) showed a direct relationship between the rate of economic growth and the level of education of the population: an increase in budgetary spending on education by 1% leads to an increase in the country's GDP by 0.35%. V. Shchetinin (2001) explains that the economy can develop only in conditions of an increase in the level of education of the workers involved in it, who make a significant contribution to social production. Pogadaeva S.S., Kharitonova N.I. (2002), Shakkum M.L. (2002) write that in world practice, special attention is paid to the problem of the impact of education on economic growth, since from 70 to 90% of GDP is determined by scientific technical progress and innovative economy. Thus, according to experts, in countries with the most developed economies, on average, 60% of the increase in national income is determined by the increase in knowledge and education of society. Similar studies were carried out by the Organization for Social and Economic Development (OECD) (Lukichev G., 2003), which showed that increasing the "education" of society for 1 academic year provides an increase in the economy of the OECD countries by 5% in the short term and by 2.5 % - in the long term.

The influence of education on economic growth was also studied in the EU countries, the

results showed (Sianesi B., Van Reenen J., 2014) that an increase in the level of education increases macroeconomic productivity, in particular: an increase in secondary education by 1 year raises production per capita by 6%; an annual increase in human capital by 1% in higher education provides an increase in the growth rate of GDP per capita by 5.9%.

Ochilov A. (2012) argues that for Uzbekistan, investment in to the quality of education can be very useful rather than investing in to the quantitative education. For education quality we have chosen the average final exam scores of students (the first attempt), while number of graduates were chosen as the best representative of education quantity (Ochilov A., 2014). Ochilov A. Ruziyev Z., Babayeva L., Ganiyeva Sh. (2020) determined that the above results suggest that one-unit change in number of educated workforces causes nearly 2 percent increases in economic growth of Uzbekistan. One-unit change in capital investments causes 0.02 percent increase in economic growth.

Analysis of publications on this issue by many authors: Cooray V, A., (2009), Gujarati, (2004), Norrag, 2012. Pawlowski, J. M., 2007. Stock J.H and Watson M.W., 2011 Atakhanov R.A. (2018) Trokhimchuk A.V. (2017) Bouhajeb M., Mefteh H., Ben Ammar R. (2018), Lafuente-Ruiz-de-Sabando A., Forcada J., Zorrilla P. (2019). Minimansurovich, A. (2014) Ahmadi, N., Black, J.L, Velazquez, E., Chapman, G.E, Veenstra, G. (2014) Rotim, M. (2013) Li, -H., Xia, E.- J. (2013), Zhang, -B. (2013), Chepel S.V. (2017) Shodiev T.Sh., Ochilov A. (2014), Ivanter V. V. (2018) showed that there is a close relationship between higher education and economic growth.

Methodology

Using annual data of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2001 to 2021, descriptive analysis and statistical tests are undertaken in addition to empirical estimations. In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens of the country are entitled to receive education. The state guarantees everyone a free general education and school education is under the supervision of the state. Empirical analysis showed that Uzbekistan has not been able to utilize its full potential leaving significant gap to be filled with recommended policy and institutional reforms. Nowadays compilation of technological development, innovations and knowledge is a credible factor of production. Thus, investments into R&D, deepening knowledge, enhancing innovations would create path for unlimited growth for Uzbekistan's economy. First, it is clear that GDP growth rate or GDP per capita growth is the best to represent economic growth. In constructing econometric models however, we selected carefully explanatory variables. During the research, we discussed and compared many versions of best representative variables of the economic growth, quantity and quality of education. One of the theories was to explain economic growth due to education quality via government investment in education sector. However, investment in education has no direct effect on education quality – it may enhance teaching tools and facilities, motivate teachers and have many other effects.

The data in the study obtained from the following sources:

- ✧ GDP per capita (Y/N): World Development Indicators and Human Development Reports
- ✧ Schooling enrolment ratio, government expenditure on education: World Bank indicators
- ✧ Student/teacher ratios: UNESCO and World Bank education statistics
- ✧ Other information: Finance Ministry, Higher and Secondary Special Education Ministry, State Statistical Committee, and Labor and Social Protection Ministry of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Overview of the higher education system and the labor market

Today, there are 178 higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan, of which 113 are local, 31 are foreign higher educational institutions and their branches. In particular, over the past 4 years, 12 new higher educational institutions, 20 branches and 24 branches of foreign higher educational institutions have been created. Based on the proposals of staff customers, the classification of directions and specialties of higher education includes 342 areas of education and 638 specialties of the magistracy. In the 2019/2020 academic year, part-time education was introduced in 59 higher educational institutions, and regime of evening-study – in 10 higher educational institutions. The number of students studying in higher educational institutions of the country amounted to 880 thousand in the bachelor's degree and 24 thousand in the magistracy, which has increased 1.6 times over the past 2 years. 52,7% of students study the humanities and pedagogical sciences, 27.1% - production and technology, 4.9% - social sphere, economics and law, 5.6% - agriculture and water management, 4.0% - health and social sphere, 5.7% are trained in specialties in the field of service education. 38.0% of undergraduates study the humanities and pedagogical sciences, 21.8% - production and technology, 15.7% - social sphere, economics and law, 6.7% - agriculture and water management, 12.4% - health and social sphere, 5.4% study in the sphere of service education. The admission parameters for the 2019/2020 academic year were 145700 people and increased by 16% compared to the previous year and by 98% compared to 2016. Since the 2018/2019 academic year, 16 universities of the country have launched joint training programs with foreign universities based on joint educational programs (Concept, 2019, Uzbekistan).

Nowadays in the national economy is going on the deep economic reforms and modernization process that requires an implementation of new of technologies for that there is need to increase the number of qualified workers. According to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in January 2022, the labor force of the republic is 19345.0 thousand people, which is 55.4% of the permanent population. The employment rate is 66.9% and the unemployment rate is 9.6%.

In recent years, the number of applicants to state and non-state universities has been more than 1 million people, and their number is increasing year after year. Admission of applicants in higher educational institutions is carried out in full-time, part-time, evening and distance learning. The number of HEI graduates and secondary special education establishments has tendency to increase over time. In the 2021-2022 academic year, the number of graduates of higher educational institutions amounted to 104,000 people, and in the 2022-2023 academic year, 135,000 graduates graduate from state universities in the regions of the republic. It is worthy to mention that thanks to implementation of the State Program on Employment each year more than 900 thousand new work places are opened in the national economy. The Uzbek universities sign long-term triangle contracts (enterprise-university-graduate) with the enterprises to employ the new graduates. For instance, in 2000 workers with higher education diploma was accounted for 20% against 28% in 2020. But the current market need for specialists in the structural terms is not match with the market supply (UNDP 2021). Despite measures taken to address organizational, financial and educational aspects, higher education in Uzbekistan currently fails to ensure training of skilled human resources that meet the new requirements of the labor market (UNDP 2021). University graduates often lack the skills for successfully developing business and knowledge of the market economy. The demand of the business sector for human resources

training is more dynamic than the ability of state educational facilities to meet them. Under these conditions, it is difficult to balance the labor market demand and supply. Consequently, social spheres: healthcare, education remain understaffed even though a sufficient number of specialists are trained. There is still a lack of engineering, mining, ICT specialists for industrial enterprises and of skilled and experienced managers for small business. With regard to labor market demand, personnel training is still problematic in other spheres. It is worthy to point out the extension of education quality effect on GDP growth of Uzbekistan. Estimation results above showed that the average years of schooling taken as proxy variable of education quality had affected on changes in economic prosperity of Uzbekistan.

Regression Models Identification

We begin our quantitative analysis of the relationship between economic growth and the higher education. The dependent variable is the GDP per capita growth, in \$1000. The regressors are the share of university graduate workers in the labor force of the economy (SHQW, in percentage), the investment in education sector, (CI in bin\$). For the model specifications, we introduce the following notations of dependent and explanatory variables: GDP per capita, in \$1000; Economic growth rate, EG, percentage; Capital Investment, CI, in billion US dollars; Capital Investment growth rate, CI, percentage; Share of the high qualified workers in the labor force, (HEI graduates), SHQW, in percentage; Total number of labor force, engaged in production, LF, in 1000 workers; Number of annual HEI graduates, DNG, in persons; Annual Growth rate of DNG, percentage.

Aggregated investments into the sectors for 1997-2021 grew by 15.9% and exceeded 26% of national income, on average, during the second and third phases of development. The efficiency of the economy (total factors productivity) grew by 4%, average, during the high growth phase. Respectively, real income of the nation grew by average 6.5% from 2006 to 2018. During 1997-2021 period numbers of qualified workers and HEI graduates grew faster than total labor force, which were accounted for respectively 3.7% and 2.5%. The average years of schooling has increased slowly, at rate of 0.8%. From 2006 to 2013, stable and moderate GDP growth rates of the country had relatively more triggered by the growth rates of labor and capital rather than that of productivity. Specifically, increasing number of highly educated and skilled labor force combined with appropriate labor market policies has contributed to the aggregate output growth during the second phase. Thanks to the improving business spheres, encouraged SMEs, comprehensive trade policies as well as increasing spending on R&D, education and social-welfare, productivity and its contribution to the country's economic growth increased significantly. According to our estimations for 2007-2017 years around 71% of the GDP, growth rates were attributable to the growth of efficiency in the economy.

Preliminary analysis concluded that productivity growth has constituted significant portion of economic growth of the country. With increasing labor factor, theory predicts that increase in the savings rate, or equally investments, leads to permanent increase in growth rates as growth in capital accumulation followed by permanent faster growth of labor never leads to diminishing returns to capital. Permanent increase in labor is obvious by the fact that there is always unemployment in any market economy.

In order to model a time series data with the Box-Jenkins approach the series has to be jointly stationary. In practical terms, the series is stationary it tends to wonder more or less uniformly about some fixed level (Stock J.H and Watson M.W.r). In statistical terms, a

stationary process assumed in particular state of statistical equilibrium, i.e. $p(x)$ is the same for all t . Because for our research the time series data is using, we conducted the Dickey-Fuller test. We built a regression lines between fractions of the current values of variables (GDP, SHQW, CI) dependent on a fraction of previous values of the series. In all cases, p -values of variables were less than 0.05 or 5%, so we rejected the null hypothesis and proceeded with econometric analysis. Our time series data is jointly stationary and we can conduct regression analysis based on OLS estimations. Our task is not to develop a forecasting model but rather to estimate causal relationships among time series variables, that is, to estimate the dynamic causal effect on Y over time of change in controlled variables.

To identify the model, firstly we needed to choose and decide which functional form to use for the research. Firstly, we develop LIN, LOG-LIN, LIN-LOG and LOG-LOG model specifications. In order to see the linear relationship between GDP growth and the share of HEI graduates in the labor force, capital investments in education, the weighted average performance rate of graduates in final exams and average years of schooling of workers in the national economy. Row (1) presents the base specification, in which the repressors are the economic growth and four control variables, the percentage of higher diploma workers in the labor force, investment in education sector, the weighted average schooling of workers and the weighted average marks of graduates in the final exams. As we can see from equation (1), high values of the economic growth rate to be associated with a future increase of all the controlled variables.

This model assumes that there is direct linear relationship between dependent and independent variables i.e. absolute change in one or more explanatory variables will cause absolute change in a dependent variable.

In LOG-LIN model, the logarithms of GDP growth rate are a dependent variable and the explanatory variables are the same as in the above model. This function assumes that absolute change in one or more independent variables will cause relative (percentage) change in dependent variable. Next, by taking the GDP per capita growth rate as the dependent variable and the share of HEI graduates in the labor force, capital investments in education sector, the weighted average performance rate of graduates in final exams and average years of schooling of workers in the national economy as independent variables we will construct LIN-LOG model. Finally, in LOG-LOG model both dependent and independent variables we took in logarithms and regressed. This function assumes that relative change in the independent variable(s) will entail relative change in the dependent variable.

Table 1 summarizes the results of regressions of the economic growth on various sets of repressors. Each row summarizes a separate regression. Each regression has the same dependent variable, economic growth rates. The entries in the first five columns are the estimated regression coefficients, with their standard errors below them in parentheses. The asterisks indicate whether the t -statistics, testing hypothesis that the relevant coefficient is zero, is significant at the 10 (one asterisk), five (two asterisks), or 1% level (three asterisks). The final two columns contain summary statistics for Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Schwarz information criterion (SIC) criterion. Regressions that include the economic growth and control variables measuring growth characteristics reported in row (1) through (4).

To choose between these functional forms four different regressions were estimated. To choose the proper model, we have to compare: (1) R^2 , (2) Akaike information criterion (AIC) and (3) Schwarz information criterion (SIC), F , and t -analysis and test coefficients on statistical

significance.

$$Y (\text{GDP per capita}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SHQW} + \beta_2 \text{CI} + \beta_3 \text{NZ} + \beta_4 \text{SPER}$$

$$\text{Log}(Y (\text{GDP per capita})) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{SHQW} + \beta_2 \text{CI} + \beta_3 \text{NZ} + \beta_4 \text{SPER}$$

$$Y (\text{GDP per capita}) = \text{Log} \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log} (\text{SHQW}) + \beta_2 \text{Log} (\text{CI}) + \beta_3 \text{Log} (\text{NZ}) + \beta_4 \text{Log} (\text{SPER})$$

$$\text{Log}(Y (\text{GDP per capita})) = \text{Log} \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log} (\text{SHQW}) + \beta_2 \text{Log} (\text{CI}) + \beta_3 \text{Log} (\text{NZ}) + \beta_4 \text{Log} (\text{SPER})$$

The values of intercept and slope coefficients are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Economic Growth Functional Specifications

Model types	Parameters					R ²	AIC	SIC
	β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4			
LIN	-10886** (2070)	154.52*** (25.81)	49.809** (13.82)	223.3* (135.9)	112.2*** (42.8)	0.98	12.7	13.08
LOG-LIN	3.621*** (0.576)	0.0462*** (0.0072)	0.0056*** (0.0038)	0.082* (0.037)	0.034** (0.01)	0.98	3.58	3.34
LIN-LOG	-51570* (9856)	2949.2*** (487.6)	320.2* (67.56)	2850* (1502.9)	8989** (2916)	0.98	12.7	12.96
LOG-LOG	-8.750* (2.751)	0.901*** (0.1361)	0.0510* (0.0188)	0.911* (0.41)	2.750** (0.81)	0.98	3.64	3.40

Notes: Robust standard errors reported in parenthesis. *, **, *** Significant at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels respectively. F-statistics respectively are 172,184,187 and 200.

We know that R² is one of the measures of goodness of fit of a regression model and it always lies between zero and one. R² explains how well independent variables fit to a dependent variable. The more it is close to 1, the more the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables used and vice versa (Gujarati, 2004). Moreover, when comparing two or more models, the model with the lowest values of AIC and SIC are preferred¹. Table 1 above summarizes the comparison of four models:

As we see from the results, the independent variables better explain the dependent variable as R² is the highest in the LIN-LIN and LOG-LOG models. As for AIC and SIC, the lowest values of them are in these models. Among these, the logarithm model satisfies all above-mentioned conditions and that we will use for further analysis. According to this regression, an additional percentage of the graduate workers' share in the labor force, investment, average schooling and weighted average graduate marks increases the economic growth respectively by 0.901, 0.051, 0.911 and 2.750 percentages. However, there is another issue to consider. As we know education, quantity measured in graduates will have effect on economic growth after some years of graduation. In other words, the quantity of educated workforce puts effort only after this workforce enters the labor market. So, one should be careful with estimating correlation between education quantity and economic growth in current stage.

To identify the quantitative influence of higher education further number of annually graduates as explanatory variable (DNG) included to the model. Different types of the specifications between economic growth and number of annually graduates and capital investment were regressed:

$$Y \text{ (GDP per capita)} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{DNG} + \alpha_2 \text{CI}$$

$$\text{Log (Y (GDP per capita))} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{DNG} + \alpha_2 \text{CI}$$

$$Y \text{ (GDP per capita)} = \text{Log } \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Log (DNG)} + \alpha_2 \text{Log (CI)}$$

$$\text{Log (Y (GDP per capita))} = \text{Log } \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Log (DNG)} + \alpha_2 \text{Log (CI)}$$

The values of intercept and slope coefficients we presented in Table 2.

Therefore, the estimation and statistical testing returned the following results:

$$Y \text{ (GDP per capita)} = 1000.55 + 0.031324\text{DNG} + 95.25628\text{CI}$$

Table 2. Higher Education Quantity Models Characteristics

Types of models	Parameters			R ²	AIG	SIG
	α_0	α_1	α_2			
LIN	1000** (207.5)	0.031*** (0.004)	95.25** (23.09)	0.925 0	14.11	14.26
LOG-LIN	7.36** * (0.061)	1.03E-05 (1.25E-06)	0.02*** (0.0068)	0.923 1	2.128	1.981
LIN-LOG	-16815. (2697)	1772.3** (256.5)	541.9* (149.9)	0.894 3	14.45	14.60
LOG-LOG	1.6167 * (0.773)	0.575*** (0.073)	0.11*** (0.043)	0.899 3	1.857	1.710

Notes: Robust standard errors reported in parenthesis. *, **, *** Significant at the 10%, 5% and 1% levels respectively.

In the Figure 1, the following info showed: GDP growth, capital investment, the number of highly qualified personnel in production, labor force, number of graduates, education censorship and higher education efficiency rates.

Figure 1. GDP growth, capital investment, the number of highly qualified personnel in production, labor force, number of graduates, education censorship and higher education efficiency rates.

All coefficients of the models are statistically significant. For the further analysis, we have selected the best-fitted specifications: the LIN-LIN and LOG-LOG models. The results in the linear specification suggest that one-unit change in a number of graduate's and capital investments causes respectively around 31 dollar and 95-dollar increase of per capita output. In the LOG-LOG model, one percent change of the number of graduates, other factors held constant, increases the economic growth by 0.57 percent and one percent change of the investment - by 0.11 percent. We assume that the unemployment rate in a country is constant and annual graduates of universities join the workforce without time lags, because all graduates in three months find the job places. The migration of the workforce we do not consider because mainly unskilled workers migrate outside of the country.

Conclusion

Assessment of data and comparison of variables pointed out that education quantity is an important determinant of economic growth. Interesting finding was that quantity and quality of education positively related to the economic growth, what indicates the importance of considering the quality of education rather than its quantity.

In the wide scope, research revealed direct relationship between economic growth and higher education quality and quantity. Although the correlation is weak, number and level of educated workforce have significant influence on economic growth. Especially, education quality is a very critical factor of steady economic expansion in very long run. The hypothesis of direct relationship between education quantity and economic growth confirmed from the estimation results. The relationship is positive but not very strong. This suggests that targeting to increase the number of educated workforces may be inefficient way of supporting economic growth or even cause fall in actual output.

Since the model is very generic, more research is necessary — specially to find specific solutions for different proxy variables of quality. Additionally, research will be initiated to analyze the differences and adaptation requirements for different proxy education quality to include lagged explanatory variables.

References

1. Ahmadi, N., Black, J.L., Velazquez, E., Chapman, G.E., Veenstra, G. Associations between socioeconomic status and school-day dietary intake in a sample of grade 5-8 students in Vancouver, Canada // *Public Health Nutrition*. - 2014. DOI: 10.1017/S1368980014001499.
2. Asminkin, Ya., Nemirovskaya, O., 2007. "Toward compulsory vocational education in Uzbekistan: A decade on," *Technical and Vocational Skills Development*, No.38, pp. 41-42.
3. Atakhanov R.A. Investments in education: theory and methodology // *Fundamental research. Economic Sciences (08.00.00)*. - 2018. - No. 1. - P. 24–28. - Access mode: <https://www.fundamental-research.ru/ru/article/view?id=42043>
4. Barro, R., 1999. "Human Capital and Growth in Cross Country Regressions," *Swedish Economic Policy Review*, Vol.6, pp. 237-277
5. Bouhajib M., Mefteh H., Ben Ammar R. Higher education and economic growth: the importance of innovation // *Atlantic rev. of economics (ARoEc)*. – 2018. – Vol. 1, N 2. – Mode of access: <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=6525858>
6. Chepel S.V. Long-term forecast of the development of the national economy and stages transition to a resource-saving model of inclusive growth // *Collection of articles of the IX Forum of economists of Uzbekistan "Ways and mechanisms of further development and liberalization*

economy in the light of the implementation of the Strategy of Action in five priority areas development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. " IPMI, MVUT, Tashkent, 2017, pp. 37-44

7. Cooray V, A., 2009. The role of education in economic growth. [online] Available from: <<http://www.uow.edu.au/content/groups/public/@web/@commerce/@econ/documents/doc/uow093025.pdf>> [Accessed 15 January 2020].

8. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" PF-5847 // People's speech, 2019.

9. Eduardo & Laurini, M, 2010. New evidence on the role of cognitive skills in Economic Development. [Online] Available from: <professores.ibmecrj.br/erg/dip_papersdp201001.pdf> [Accessed 15 January 2020].

10. Gujarati, 2004. *Basic Econometrics*, 4th ed., the McGraw-Hill, USA. Pages 536-537

11. Hanushek, A, E & Kimko, D, D., 2000. Schooling, Labor-Force Quality, and the Growth of Nations, [online] Available from: <<http://www.usrcampaniapoliticheformative.org/uploads/Nations.pdf>> [Accessed 15 January 2020].

12. Hanushek, A, E & Woessmann L, 2007. The Role of Cognitive Skills in Economic Development. [online] Available from: <<http://hanushek.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/publications.pdf>> [Accessed 15 January, 2020].

13. Ivanter V. V. On the issue of economic growth. The economic revival of Russia. – № 2 (56). – 2018. – pp.14-16

14. Kozma, B, R., 2008. ICT, Education Reform, and Economic Growth: A Conceptual Framework. [Online] Available from: <http://download.intel.com/education/HP/Kozma_WP1.pdf> [Accessed 20 January 2020].

15. Lafuente-Ruiz-de-Sabando A., Forcada J., Zorrilla P. The university image: a model of overall image and stakeholder perspectives // Cuadernos de gestión. – 2019. – Vol. 19, N 1. – P. 63–86. – Mode of access: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326380276_The_university_image_a_model_of_overall_image_and_stakeholder_perspectives

16. Li, -H., Xia, E.-J. Research on influence of human capital on the economy growth based on the extended solow model // International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Annual Conference Proceedings. - 2013. - pp. 1460-1465.

17. Lukichev G. USA and the European Union: Competition in Education and Research // In the world of science. - 2003. - No. 10. - p.18-19.

18. Maddison A. Dynamic Forces in Capitalist Development. - Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1991. - p. 37-43.

19. Minimansurovich, A. Processes of reforming teacher training in modern Russia (Experience of the Kazan Federal University) // American Journal of Applied Sciences. - 2014. -№11 (8). - pp. 1365-1368. DOI: 10.3844/ajassp.2014.1365.1368.

20. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn meeting dedicated to the Day of teachers and mentors. 09/30/2020. A source: <http://uza.uz/ru/posts/vystuplenie-prezidenta-respubliki-uzbekistan-shavkata-mirziye-30.09.2020>

21. Norrag, 2012. Toward compulsory vocational education in Uzbekistan: A decade on. [online] Available from: < <http://www.norrag.org/issues/article/1035/en/toward-compulsory-vocational-education-in-uzbekistan-a-decade-on.html> > [Accessed 17 February 2020].
22. Ochilov A. et al. Education and economic growth in Uzbekistan // Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business, PIEB. – 2012. – T. 12. – №. 3. – C. 21-33.
23. Ochilov A. et al. Is higher education a driving force of economic growth in Uzbekistan? // Perspectives of Innovations, Economics and Business, PIEB. – 2014. – T. 14. – №. 4. – C. 160-174.
24. Ochilov A.O. The Higher Education Dynamics and Economic Growth: The Case of Uzbekistan // Journal of Management Value & Ethics. – India, 2017. – Vol. 7. – No. 2 (Apr.-June). – P. 46-53.
25. Ochilov A. Ruziyev Z., Babayeva L., Ganiyeva Sh. Highly qualified personnel as a factor in increasing economic growth in Uzbekistan // International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. Vol. 24, Issue 09, 2020. – pp. 3867-3880.
26. Pawlowski, J. M., 2007. The Quality Adaptation Model: Adaptation and Adoption of the Quality Standard ISO/IEC 19796-1 for *Learning, Education, and Training*. *Educational Technology & Society*, 10 (2), 3-16
27. Pogadaeva SS, Kharitonova NI Regional aspects of sustainable development on the example of the Kemerovo region [Electronic resource] // Economy of Russia: theory and modernity: materials of 2 Chayanovskih readings. - Moscow, 2002. - URL: <http://bookbk.net/book/34-kognomika-karpenko-mp/7-14kognitivnyj-chelovek-yekonomika-i-obrazovanie.html>.
28. Pritchett, L, 1996. Where Has All the Education Gone? [Online] Available from: < <http://unpan1.un.org/intradoc/groups/public/documents/unpan/unpan002390.pdf> > [Accessed 20 January 2022].
29. Rotim, M. Relevance and realization of communication between information and communication technology employers and educational sector // 36th International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics: MIPRO 2013 - - 2013. - pp. 770-775.
30. Shchetinin V. Human capital and the ambiguity of its interpretation // World Economy and International Relations. - 2001. - No. 12. - p.42-49.
31. Shakkum ML High technologies in the military-industrial complex are not yet available, but ... // Patriot, - June 27. 2002. - p.3.
32. Shodiev T.Sh., Ochilov A., 2014. “An empirical analysis of higher education and economic growth in Uzbekistan,” Effective use of social-economic potential and draw into new sources of economic growth. VI th materials of young economist scientists, Tashkent, IFMR, 1, pp.243-249.
33. Stock J.H and Watson M.W.,2011, Introduction to Econometrics. Third edition. Addison-Wesley. PP.517-520
34. Trokhimchuk A.V. The impact of education on the economy in a post-industrial society // Scientific and methodological electronic journal "Concept". - 2017. - T. 14. - P. 292–298. - Access mode: <http://e-koncept.ru/2017/770663.htm>
35. UNDP National Report “Education in Uzbekistan: Matching Supply and Demand “*NHDR2007/2008*”, [Online] the UNDP (www.undp.uz). Policy brief • 1 (12) • 2019
36. The World Bank, 2019. Uzbekistan. [Online] Available from: <<http://data.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan>> [Accessed 25 February 2022].

37. UNDP, 2019. National Human Development Report 2007-2008. Education in Uzbekistan: Matching Supply and Demand. [Online] Available from: <<http://www.undp.uz/en/publications/publication.php?id=100>> [Accessed 25 January 2022].
38. UZA, 2021. Address by President Islam Karimov at the Opening Ceremony of International Conference. [Online] Available from: <<http://uza.uz/en/politics/2470/>> [Accessed 19 February 2022].
39. Zhang, -B. National Education and Global Economic Growth: A Synthesis of the Uzawa-Lucas Two-Sector and the Oniki-Uzawa Trade Models // Journal of the Knowledge Economy. - 2013. - pp. 1-24.
40. <https://ru.wikipedia.org> [Accessed 19 February 2022].